

APPLICATION OF AN EXPERT SYSTEM TO DESIGN METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

An expert system prototype has been developed to aid in the selection and design of metal matrix composites[1]. The system which has been developed within the Comdale/X environment manages material property databases and a mathematical analysis applications tool. The capabilities of the system will be demonstrated through the analysis of a consultation session.

INTRODUCTION

The selection of a specific material for a particular application requires familiarity with available materials, their properties, and suitable fabrication routes[2]. This information may be divided into that which is used directly in design calculations and that which is not[3]. Numerical material property data can be efficiently stored in databases. However, disadvantages of database systems include their inability to adequately represent experience-based and other non-quantitative information from experts and handle missing or uncertain data[4-6]. If a database is complete, then simple and powerful indexing and search techniques are possible; however, sparse databases are far less easy to use since searches conducted for particular property values reject materials whose properties are absent or not yet measured. This is the case of metal matrix composites where a lack of material property measurements is one factor which limits their widespread use.

The decision to employ advanced materials like metal matrix composites is complicated by the fact that the materials designer must choose an appropriate reinforcement/matrix combination to meet the design needs. Mathematical modeling which relates the properties of the constituent matrix and reinforcement to that of the composite material is a technique employed in this expert system to aid in the selection and design of metal matrix composites and fill in property gaps.

The representation of experience-based and non-quantitative information is effectively achieved with an expert system. Expert systems employ a number of techniques to capture and imitate the decision-making of human experts in certain narrow domains of knowledge. The knowledge of this system encompasses mechanical and thermophysical properties databases of matrix alloys, reinforcements and MMCs; associated information; effective composite properties prediction capabilities; constituent material compatibility and selection guidelines; manufacturing and cost

information. In order to demonstrate the capabilities of this expert system, the results of a sample consultation are described.

CONSULTATION OBJECTIVE

The most commonly used alloys for cryogenic applications are austenitic stainless steels, nickel steels, and aluminum alloys[7]. Some typical alloys and their properties are shown in Table 1. For service temperatures down to 4 K, the austenitic stainless steels and aluminum alloys are the preferred alloys [8]. The wider application of aluminum alloys has been hampered by their low modulus of elasticity and strength, high thermal conductivity, and high coefficient of thermal expansion[7]. A low ratio of thermal conductivity to elastic modulus reduces refrigeration costs whenever the components are subjected to a temperature gradient. A low coefficient of thermal expansion(CTE) is also an important design parameter since additional stresses are introduced into the structure in the presence of a temperature gradient. The advantages of aluminum alloys include their low density, nonmagnetic behavior, weldability, compatibility with cryogenics; and retained strength, fracture toughness and elongation at low temperatures.

Table 1. Typical Properties of Cryogenic Materials at Room Temperature[7,9,10]

Material Designation	Density (g/cm ³)	Yield Strength (MPa)	Ultimate Tensile Strength (MPa)	Modulus of Elasticity (GPa)	Poisson's Ratio	Thermal Conductivity (W/mK)	Coefficient of Thermal Expansion (x 10 ⁻⁶ /K)
<i>Steels</i>							
ASTM A203 grade D alloy steel	7.86	255	448	204	0.28	35	11.9
ASTM A516 grade 55 carbon steel	7.83	207	379	195	0.28	50	11.75
ASTM A240 AISI 304 austenitic s.s.	8.03	207	517	193	0.29	17	15.8
<i>Aluminum Alloys</i>							
2219-T87	2.84	395	475	73	0.33	120	23
5083-O	2.66	145	290	72	0.33	117	23
6061-T6	2.7	275	310	70	0.34	167	23

In practice, welded austenitic stainless steel assemblies are widely used but they are expensive; the toughness of the welds is usually significantly lower than the base metal; and there is an increased sensitivity to hydrogen embrittlement in the welds[7,8]. Substitution of these welded assemblies by machined and bolted high strength aluminum alloys has been proposed. However, the coefficient of thermal expansion mismatch between the aluminum alloys and the steel bolts is a major barrier. The mismatch in CTE of aluminum and steel alloys is also a problem in the design of double-wall vessels and in many instances is the deciding factor in the selection of the inner and outer tank material[9]. The substitution of austenitic stainless steels is the goal of this consultation.

METAL MATRIX COMPOSITE DATABASE SEARCH

The necessary requirement for all candidate MMCs will be a CTE equivalent to austenitic stainless steels, a lower thermal conductivity, and an increase in the elastic modulus. In this case, a room temperature CTE value of 15.8 x10⁻⁶/K, equivalent to AISI 304 SS in Table 1, is selected. The first step in the consultation is to search the MMC database to identify possible candidate materials. It was decided to access the database independent of the expert system interface since the number of entries is relatively small and can be browsed efficiently using the features of Microsoft Excel. The system is designed with this flexibility so that the user can

easily switch to other Microsoft Windows applications during a consultation, or can update and add new information to the Excel databases either during a consultation or when running Excel independently.

A list of materials retrieved from the MMC database search are shown in Table 2. Thermal conductivity values retrieved from the database for these materials reveal an increase over the monolithic matrix alloy thereby precluding their further consideration. At this juncture the option to explore designing a composite with a matrix/alloy combination meeting the design objectives is undertaken.

Table 2. Materials Retrieved From MMC Database

Material Designation	Coefficient of Thermal Expansion ($\times 10^{-6}/K$)
X2080/SiC/15p	15.5
2024/SiC/25F-T6	14.9L 16.4T
6092/SiC/25p-T6	15.3
6090/SiC/25p-T6	15.3
6090H/SiC/25p	15.3

METAL MATRIX COMPOSITE MATERIAL DESIGN

The first task is to select appropriate alloy matrices. In this consultation, two aluminum alloys currently used at cryogenic temperatures namely, the high strength alloy 2219-T87 and the medium strength alloy 6061-T6 will be used. Alternatively, other matrix alloys may be selected from the matrix alloy database of this system which includes properties for many copper, aluminum, titanium, and magnesium alloys. Selection of reinforcement materials is more complex. Browsing through the reinforcement database of the system, it is evident that the majority of the reinforcements possess superior stiffness (relative to the aluminum matrices) and low coefficients of thermal expansion.

The dilemma of materials selection is determining the best method to follow. A consensus on the approach of materials selection has not evolved and no single or small number of methods have emerged to a position of prominence [4,11-14]. Therefore, an approach has been formulated in this work to combine an elimination process common to most selection databases with a semi-qualitative method of a knowledge base and on-line hypertext interface.

The thermal conductivity of reinforcements varies widely. In order to prepare a shortlist of potential reinforcements, their value will be subjectively limited to 30 W/mK or less. This threshold value is selected by the user to generate the list shown in Table 3. Due to uncertainty associated with many published values, degrees of belief associated with the property values are given in the database to aid in the selection process. Property values of different materials do not have the same reliability and cannot be compared simply based on one database entry. For example, the average value of thermal conductivity for B_4C particulate is 48 W/mK; however, the range is approximately 29 - 67 W/mK. With a database entry of 48 W/mK, B_4C_p would have been overlooked by the majority of database management systems. This expert system will retrieve ranges of property values in addition to degrees of belief in these values, therefore ensuring materials such as B_4C_p are identified.

The final selection of reinforcements for consideration is made qualitatively. The expert system is employed to examine information on matrix/reinforcement compatibility, reinforcement cost and elastic modulus. From the particulate category, the two particulates with the highest

modulus of elasticity and comparable cost were selected, namely TiB₂ and B₄C. From the whisker/short fiber category, two whisker reinforcements, B₄C and Al₂O₃, and the short fiber Al₂O₃ saffil RF were selected based on their higher elastic moduli. The two fibers selected are SiC SCS-2 fiber with a high modulus and high cost and Al₂O₃ - Nextel 312 with a lower modulus and lower cost.

Table 3. Reinforcements Retrieved From Database

Particulates	Whisker/Short Fibers	Fibers	
Al ₂ O ₃	Al ₂ O ₃	Al ₂ O ₃ - Nextel 312	C fiber PAN E-34
B ₄ C	Al ₂ O ₃ -SiO ₂ Fiberfrax	Al ₂ O ₃ - Nextel 440	SiC fiber SCS
Si ₃ N ₄	Al ₂ O ₃ -Saffil RF Grade	Al ₂ O ₃ -Safimax	SiC fiber on W
TiB ₂	B ₄ C	Al ₂ O ₃ -Fiber FP DuPont	SiC fiber on C
TiC	SNW Si ₃ N ₄ whisker	Al ₂ O ₃ - SiO ₂ Sumitomo	SiCf Nicalon NL = 200
		Al ₂ O ₃ - SiO ₂ Fibermax	TiB ₂
		C fiber PAN HTS(T300)	

Table 4. Constituent Properties

Material	Density (g/cm ³)	Modulus of Elasticity (GPa)	Poisson's ratio	Thermal Conductivity (W/mK)	Coefficient of Thermal Expansion (x10 ⁻⁶ /K)
Al alloy 2219-T87	2.84	73	0.33	120	23
Al alloy 6061-T6	2.7	70	0.34	167	23
B ₄ C particulate	2.52	450	0.25	29	5
TiB ₂ particulate	4.52	510	0.18	25	8.3
Al ₂ O ₃ fiber Nextel 312	2.7	154	0.25	24	3.5
SiC fiber SCS-2	3.0	400	0.25	16	3
Al ₂ O ₃ whisker (L/d = 10)	3.96	450	0.25	24	7.7
B ₄ C whisker (L/d = 10)	2.52	490	0.21	28	6.08
Al ₂ O ₃ short fiber saffil RF (L/d = 20)	3.3	310	0.22	24	8

EFFECTIVE MMC PROPERTY PREDICTION

The prediction of effective composite properties is achieved using established mathematical models located in an external applications tool Microsoft Excel[1]. The system employs appropriate models depending on reinforcement shape and geometry to predict effective composite properties. The requisite constituent properties for this example are retrieved from the matrix alloy and reinforcement databases and are listed in Table 4. The volume fraction of reinforcement which gives the target CTE of 15.8 x10⁻⁶/K are determined as shown in Tables 5-7 for the particulate, whisker/short fiber, and fiber reinforcements respectively.

Table 5. Particulate Reinforced MMC Coefficient of Thermal Expansion(x 10⁻⁶/K)[1]

Material Designation	Turner Equation	Hashin-Shtrikman Bounds	
		lower ^a	upper
2219/B ₄ C/22p	13.3	15.7	18.0
6061/B ₄ C/22p	13.3	15.8	18.1
2219/TiB ₂ /29p	14.1	15.7	17.8
6061/ TiB ₂ /29p	14.2	15.8	17.9

a = Kerner Method etc.

Table 6. Whisker/Short Fiber Reinforced MMC Coefficient of Thermal Expansion($\times 10^{-6}/K$)[1]

Material Designation	Randomly Distributed	Aligned Longitudinal		Aligned Transverse	
	Halpin & Pagano	Halpin Equation	Marom & Weinberg	Halpin Equation	Hashin Strikman Bounds
2219/Al ₂ O ₃ /27w (L/d = 10)	15.7	14.2	14.2	20.5	lower 15.8 upper 17.9
2219/B ₄ C/22w (L/d = 10)	15.8	14.7	14	21	16.1 18.4
2219/Al ₂ O ₃ /32sf (L/d = 20)	15.8	14.9	14.8	19.5	16.2 17.4
6061/Al ₂ O ₃ /27w (L/d = 10)	15.6	14.3	14	20.6	15.8 18
6061/B ₄ C/22w (L/d = 10)	15.8	14.7	13.8	21.1	16.2 18.4
6061/Al ₂ O ₃ /32sf (L/d = 20)	15.8	15	14.7	19.6	16.3 17.5

Table 7. Fiber Reinforced MMC Coefficient of Thermal Expansion($\times 10^{-6}/K$)[1]

Material Designation	Randomly Distributed	Aligned Longitudinal			Aligned Transverse		
	Craft & Christensen	Schapery	CCM ^a	Eshelby	Schapery	CCM ^a	Eshelby
2219/Al ₂ O ₃ /35f	15.7	12.6	13	14.8	17.6	17	15.9
2219/SiC/27f	15.7	9.6	9.9	13.1	20.4	19.2	17.7
6061/Al ₂ O ₃ /35f	15.7	12.4	12.9	14.7	17.7	17.1	16
6061/SiC/27f	15.8	9.4	9.7	13	20.5	19.4	17.9

a = Composite Cylinders Model

The effective thermal conductivity and elastic modulus of these materials is then determined for the MMCs of Table 5-7[1]. Figure 1 is a screen view of the input interface for predicting properties necessary to determine effective modulus for 2219/Al₂O₃/32sf. An important feature is the ability of the user to alter values retrieved from the databases or input new values. Consequently, the user may employ this feature to predict effective composite properties for matrix/reinforcement combinations not found in the system.

Prediction of Effective Modulus of Elasticity

Done Undo

Input values to be used by MMCxpert effective composite E calculation.
Alter any information if desired (Use the Tab key/mouse to scroll down.)

Matrix name:

Matrix E (GPa):

Matrix poisson's ratio:

Type of Reinforcement:

Fiber Yes No Whisker Yes No

Short Fiber Yes No Particulate Yes No

Reinforcement name:

Reinforcement modulus E (GPa):

Reinforcement poisson's ratio:

Volume Percent of Reinforcement:

Whisker/Short Fiber Aspect Ratio:

Figure 1. Screen View of Input for Effective Modulus Prediction

Figure 2 is the next screen view showing the results of the calculations for effective elastic modulus. The on-line information hypertext document includes pertinent information on the mathematical models and general information on material behavior. This document is accessed in order to gain information on thermal conductivity, coefficient of thermal expansion and elastic modulus of MMC materials and the models themselves. The Excel spreadsheet performing the calculations can also be accessed during the consultation to view graphical representations of the models.

Modulus of Elasticity				
Done		Undo		
SUMMARY				
Whisker/Short Fiber Reinforced MMCs				
Mathematical Model Results				
1. RANDOMLY ORIENTED		Modulus E (GPa)		
Hatta_Taya		124		
Tsai_Pagano [E Input from Eshelby]		124		
2. ALIGNED		Longitudinal[axial] Direction		Transverse Direction
Hashin-Shtrikman Bounds		Upper	135	Lower 117
Eshelby Method			148	109
Halpin-Tsai			145	-
Behrens'			-	99
3. MODEL PARAMETERS		E (GPa)	Poisson's Ratio	
Al alloy 2219		73	0.33	Volume Percent 32
Al2O3-Saffil RF grade		310	0.22	Aspect Ratio L/D 20

Figure 2. Screen View of Effective Modulus Prediction Results

ANALYSIS

Having obtained effective property values for the candidate metal matrix materials, the decision as to which materials warrant further investigation must be made. For the particulate composites of Table 5, the effective modulus is primarily dependent on the volume fraction of the reinforcement whereas thermal conductivity is strongly influenced by the matrix value. For the whisker, short fiber and fiber composites of Tables 6 and 7, the aspect ratio and geometry of the reinforcement phase also play a large role on the effective composite modulus and thermal conductivity properties. For example, the results shown in Figure 2 demonstrate the difference between longitudinal and transverse directions on the elastic modulus of aligned 2219/Al₂O₃/32sf. However, depending upon design requirements, a poor longitudinal or transverse property value may not be a primary factor in the selection decision.

Table 8 contains effective thermal conductivity K, elastic modulus E, and thermal conductivity to elastic modulus ratio K/E for these materials with a random reinforcement distribution. Significant improvements in the K/E ratio are evident for all candidate materials when compared to the monolithic aluminum alloys. Specifically, 10 out of the 14 materials in the list give a twofold or better improvement in the K/E ratio of the monolithic alloys. If this is an acceptable design target, then these 10 materials warrant further examination.

Table 8. Thermal Conductivity to Elastic Modulus Ratio for Candidate MMCs[1]

Material Designation	Elastic Modulus E ^a (GPa)	Thermal Conductivity K ^b (W/mK)	K/E Ratio
2219/TiB ₂ /29p	140	82	0.59
2219/Al ₂ O ₃ /27w	135	82	0.61
2219/Al ₂ O ₃ /32sf	124	76	0.61
2219/SiC/27f	123	84	0.68
2219/B ₄ C/22w	127	91	0.72
2219/B ₄ C/22p	121	92	0.76
6061/TiB ₂ /29p	136	109	0.80
6061/Al ₂ O ₃ /32sf	122	100	0.82
2219/Al ₂ O ₃ /35f	96	79	0.82
6061/Al ₂ O ₃ /27w	132	110	0.83
6061/SiC/27f	120	115	0.96
6061/B ₄ C/22w	124	122	0.98
6061/B ₄ C/22p	117	124	1.06
6061/Al ₂ O ₃ /35f	93	106	1.14
5083-O	72	117	1.63
2219-T87	73	120	1.64
6061-T6	70	167	2.39

a = particulate: Paul Model, whisker/short fiber: Hatta & Taya Eqn, Fiber: Christensen & Waals 2D

b = particulate: Lewis & Nielsen, whisker/short fiber: Lewis & Nielsen, fiber: Hashin-Shtrikman upper bound

To focus in on a shortlist of candidates, the MMCs with the lowest K/E ratio will be examined. Again, the problem of setting a performance threshold presents itself. If the K/E ratio is set at 0.8, then 6061/TiB₂/29p passes but 6061/Al₂O₃/32sf does not. This is not a fair representation since the properties of the short fiber composite can be varied according to the reinforcement geometry to surpass the particulate composite. The selection of 2219/TiB₂/29p, 2219/Al₂O₃/27w, 2219/Al₂O₃/32sf, and 2219/SiC/27f from Table 8 is accompanied by the following observation: they represent all four categories of particulate, whisker, short fiber, and fiber reinforced composites; and they are based on a 2219 matrix alloy. This illustrates the importance of the initial alloy selection and the competitiveness of differing reinforcement types.

The selection of candidate materials in effect is a trade-off between performance and cost. Manufacturing methods influence both cost and effective composite properties. Based upon constituent compatibility, volume fraction and reinforcement type, information is provided by the system which advises on appropriate manufacturing routes. This module is in its early stages of development thus constraints due to phase geometry, reinforcement damage, cost and product shape are currently not considered. A heuristic method using linguistic variables is employed. A database of reinforcement cost information with sources and dates is available which can be updated by the user. Heuristic information on the relative cost of some manufacturing processes is also available.

For the four materials, 2219/TiB₂/29p, 2219/Al₂O₃/27w, 2219/Al₂O₃/32sf, and 2219/SiC/27f; manufacturing costs of the fiber reinforced composite is highest at this time and probably too costly. Consulting the system on 2219/TiB₂/29p, TiB₂ powder costs between 35 - 65 US \$/kg (1993) depending on grade and purity. The manufacturing routes suggested include: melt infiltration, spray casting and powder metallurgy. Squeeze casting of highly loaded preforms of TiB₂ has been performed successfully. Specific cost information on Al₂O₃ whiskers is not available but is comparable to TiB₂ particulates. The cost of Saffil short fiber 25 v/o preforms are estimated at 22 US \$/kg. The system advises that Al₂O₃ is nonwetting in aluminum. SiO₂ additions are typically made and aluminum alloys containing appreciable amounts of elements whose oxides are more stable than Al₂O₃(e.g. Mg & Li) will attack the reinforcement. The

system lists Ni, Cu, Ti, B, Ti, TiB, immersion in molten Na and SiO₂ as potential coatings for Al₂O₃ in aluminum. The Al₂O₃ whiskers will need coating whereas the Saffil Al₂O₃ already contains SiO₂. Successful manufacture of squeeze cast Saffil reinforced aluminum composites has been accomplished.

It is evident that the complexity of the comparisons and trade-offs make a clear decision difficult. The final step is to determine what other information is needed. Specific components must be identified and design parameters established to determine the suitability of aligned versus randomly distributed reinforced materials. Material constraints such as reinforcement geometry and shape due to manufacturing methods must be established. The selection of less expensive alloys or reinforcements for comparison may be in order (e.g. Al₂O₃p for Al₂O₃w). An iterative consultation process is necessary to determine the full potential of alternative MMC candidates.

CONCLUSION

An expert system prototype has been developed which aids design engineers in the selection and design of metal matrix composite materials. This example consultation has shown the need for experience-based and non-quantitative information in the selection process and highlights the problems encountered with database systems. The use of mathematical modeling to predict properties and infer knowledge, an on-line hypertext document containing extensive materials information and the management of the databases with the expert system combine to form a powerful design tool.

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